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Tomato Cultivation in Different Soil Covers

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Resumo:

A mudança em direção à sustentabilidade é uma tendência na agricultura hoje. Mudar os sistemas de produção agrícola com base nas técnicas tradicionais é uma necessidade, principalmente devido à crescente preocupação com o meio ambiente e a qualidade dos produtos. Assim, o objetivo deste estudo foi avaliar as diferentes coberturas do solo no cultivo do tomate. As coberturas estudadas foram dispostas em delineamento de blocos casualizados, com 4 coberturas, sendo as coberturas utilizadas: cobertura viva (amendoim forrageiro), palhada (palha de crotalaria e milho), cobertura plástica branca e sem cobertura morta / capina. Altura da planta, número de folhas e diâmetro do caule foram avaliados até 30 dias após o transplante (DAT). Aos 30 DAT, foram avaliadas a clorofila a, clorofila b e clorofila total. A colheita foi realizada manualmente, avaliando-se a massa fresca dos frutos, o número de frutos por planta-1 e os parâmetros de cor (a^* , b^* e L^*). A cobertura plástica branca foi superior às demais coberturas de solo, onde foram observadas plantas com maior diâmetro do caule, maior número de frutos por planta e frutos com pericarpo menos amarelado.

Palavras-chave: *Solanum lycopersicum*; sistema de cultivo; cobertura plástica, cobertura viva, palhada.

Abstract:

Moving towards sustainability is a trend in agriculture today. Changing agricultural production systems based on traditional techniques is a necessity, mainly due to the growing concern with environmental and product quality. Thus, the aim of this study was to evaluate the different soil cover in tomato cultivation. The coverings studied were arranged in a randomized block design, with 4 coverings, being the coverings used: live covering (forage peanut), mulch (crotalaria straw and millet), mulching and without mulch/hoeing. Plant height, number of leaves and stem diameter were evaluated up to 30 days after transplanting (DAT). At 30 DAT, chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b and total chlorophyll were evaluated. The harvest was carried out manually, and the fresh fruit mass, the number of fruits per plant-1 and the color parameters (a^* , b^* and L^*) were evaluated. The white plastic cover was superior to the other soil covers, where plants with larger stem diameter, a greater number of fruits per plant and fruits with less yellow pericarp color were observed.

Keys-word: *Solanum lycopersicum*; tillage system; plastic cover, live cover, straw.

INTRODUCTION

Inserting techniques that cause less damage to the environment is a hot topic for agriculture. Agricultural cultivation techniques traditionally used are not always based on concern for the environment. Studies have shown that in agriculture, it is possible to combine profitability with sustainability; favoring the preservation and conservation of natural resources.

Conservationist/agroecological practices are based on the use of techniques that mitigate the impacts triggered by traditional agriculture; such as crop rotation; reduction in the use of agrochemicals; optimization of irrigation systems for better use of water; optimization of already arable areas; and the use of ground covers, among many others. In addition to the permanence and independence of small farmers (SANTOS et al., 2014).

Ground cover is a widespread practice in vegetable production; being a condition to increase the quality of production and productivity of these species (LOPES et al., 2011). Among the advantages of the technique, we can mention: water savings, triggered by the reduction of water evaporation from the ground; the reduction of soil temperature, due to the physical protection that the cover provides; increase in soil organic matter content; what favors soil structuring and soil microbial fauna; what, together, contribute to

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the physical, chemical and biological improvement of the soil. The coverage also contributes to the suppression of the emergence of invasive plants in the cultivation area, which directly impacts the reduction of inputs in production costs and environmental quality with the reduction of herbicide applications. The choice of coverage is mainly influenced by the technification of the producer and the climatic conditions in the region; for example, the color of the plastic cover will increase or reduce the influence of temperature under the soil (HIRATA et al. 2009; LIMA JUNIOR & LOPES, 2009; LAMBERT et al., 2017).

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) is a vegetable grown and consumed all over the world. Some conservation practices are already being applied in tomatoculture. For Hirata (2009), the use of ground cover in tomato cultivation reflects on the physical, chemical and biological quality of the soil; mainly in the suppression of weed emergence in tomato crops.

Mendonça et al. (2021) using plastic covering in tomato plants observed a reduction in soil temperature and an increase in the growth of tomato plants. Marouelli, Silva, Madeira (2006), verifying the efficiency of water use and the production of tomato for processing in a no-tillage system with forage sorghum straw, observed a higher fruit yield with a greater efficiency in the use of water. In terms of live soil cover, forage peanuts (*Arachis pintoi*) have been widely used in tomato production, where they observed an increase in production and in the number of commercial fruits (RESENDE, VILELA, SOUZA; 2020).

Daniel and Dalbianco (2021), verifying the temperature and humidity of the soil cultivated with Taise tomato in different soil coverings, noticed that the mulching and millet coverings presented the highest production of commercial fruits and soil moisture. The soil temperature was higher in the mulching was the one with the highest soil temperature, however, the greatest thermal amplitude. Hirata et al. (2009) evaluating straw production and weed suppression by cover crops found that *Pennisetum glaucum*, *Crotalaria juncea* and *Stizolobium aterrimum* straw produced more than 20 Mg ha⁻¹ of dry matter and reduced weed emergence in the crop. of ground tomato.

In this context, the aim of this study was to evaluate the effect of four soil coverings in the cultivation of ground tomato with a table focus and its effect on development and production, in Goiânia – Goiás.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study took place in the experimental area of the Horticulture Sector of the School of Agronomy of the Federal University of Goiás in the city of Goiânia – Goiás (latitude 16°35'12" S, longitude 49°21'14" W Gr, at 730 m altitude). According to Koppen's climatological classification, the region's climate is Aw (SANTANA, 2015), with a potential water deficit between June and August and global solar irradiance significantly increasing between September and October (Figure 1). The observed potential evapotranspiration and maximum, mean and minimum air temperatures (Figure 2) were collected at the meteorological station in the Horticulture Sector.

Figure 1. Distribution of rainfall and insolation over the experimental area in 2019.

Figure 2. Distribution of air temperature and evapotranspiration throughout 2019.

The study area had soil with the following characteristics: at a depth of 0-20 cm, pH-CaCl₂ (5.8), P-Mehlich (90.0 mg/dm³), K (64.0 mg/dm³), Ca (3.9 cmol/dm³), Mg (1.2 cmol/dm³), Al (0.0 cmol/dm³), H+Al (2.2 cmol/dm³), organic matter (18.0 g/dm³); with 46% clay, 44% sand and 10% silt. The soil preparation of the area was conventional, with plowing at 0.25 m of depth and harrowing; distribution of dolomitic limestone (PRNT 100%) and soil leveling.

The study was arranged in a randomized block design, where four soil covers were tested for the cultivation of industrial tomato with a tabletop approach; of which: live mulch (forage peanut), mulch (crotalaria straw and millet), mulching and hand weeding.

The genotype CVR 2909 (Vivati Plant Breeding - resistant to *Verticillium dahlie*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Meloidogyne incognita* and *M. javanica*) was used. To obtain the mulch, 60 days before transplanting (DAT) the tomato plant was sown sunn hemp (*Crotalaria juncea*) and millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*); these crops are crushed at the time of flowering to form straw in the beds. For live coverage, forage peanut (*Arachis pintoi*) was sown 60 days before tomato transplantation. In the beds referring to white plastic cover was applied 60 days before transplanting the seedlings. In the treatment of manual weeding, weed control was carried out weekly with the aid of a hoe.

Up to 30 days after transplanting the seedlings, weekly monitoring was carried out: a) plant height: with the aid of a graduated tape, with results expressed in cm; b) the number of sheets: counting the number of expanded sheets; c) stem diameter: with the aid of a digital caliper, with results expressed in mm; d) At 30 days after transplanting, the chlorophyll a, b and total content of the expanded leaves of the industrial tomato plant was measured using the SPAD-502 chlorophyll meter (Minolta).

The harvest was done manually, when the plants already had 90% of the fruits ripe; and it was evaluated: e) fresh fruit mass: using a digital scale, expressed in kg; f) number of fruits: counting the number of ripe and commercial fruits; g) pericarp color parameters: color determination was performed by reflectance, by reading the L*, a* and b* parameters of the CIELAB system. With a ColorQuest XE colorimeter.

The means of the studied variables were subjected to analysis of variance and when significant, regression was applied for quantitative variables and Tukey's test for qualitative variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

There was a significant difference between the initial development parameters of the ground tomato as a function of the different ground cover. Figure 3(A) shows the height of tomato plants, 3(B) stem diameter and 3(C) number of leaves from 7 to 28 DAT.

Plant height presented a linear growth for all coverings. Plants cultivated under White plastic cover and under straw showed the highest increases in plant height up to 28 DAT, however they did not differ from the other coverings. Regarding the number of leaves, it was observed that the treatment without

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mulches/hoeing presented higher values than the other treatments and that the liver cover treatment presented less leaves. The same was observed for stem diameter. This result of a smaller number of leaves and stem diameter in the liver cover treatment was probably due to the competition of the green cover with the tomato crop for nutrients, water, light, and carbon dioxide (CO₂), in addition to the presence of peanuts. Forage planters may have contributed to the creation of a microclimate close to tomato plants, favoring the occurrence of diseases, in addition to hosting pest insects, which may have contributed to the decrease in the number of leaves. (CASTRO et al., 2016).

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Figure 3 Plant height (A), number of fruits (B) and stem diameter (C) of the ground tomato plant as a function of different ground cover.

Stem diameter showed superior results for the white plastic cover and straw treatment compared to the other treatments, stems with larger diameter are favorable to field production, since they provide greater resistance to abiotic factors, such as wind and rain, favoring production of the fruits (FERREIRA et al., 2017).

Figure 4 shows the levels of chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b and total chlorophyll in the ground tomato. None of the soil covers showed significant difference for the analyzed chlorophyll contents.

Figure 4 Chlorophyll a, b and total contents in ground tomato as a function of ground cover. Different letters differ statistically from each other, by Tukey's test at 5% probability.

Schuelter et al. (2003) also found no statistical difference in chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b and total chlorophyll, when evaluating the levels of chlorophyll in tomato leaves of cultivar Santa Cruz, at 30 and 60 days of cultivation, on the first, second and third leaves.

Figure 5 shows the mass of fruits per plant and the number of fruits of ground tomato in different soil coverings. For fruit mass per plant a statistical difference was observed, where the lowest averages were observed in the live cover. For number of fruits per plant, the highest averages were observed in the

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coverings with White plastic cover and whitout mulch/hoeing, with averages of 57.16 and 54.16 fruits plant⁻¹, respectively.

The live cover showed plants with less fruit and less mass, which may be a result of competition between tomato and live cover (forage peanut) for nutrients, water and solar irradiation, similar results were observed by (Silva et al., 2010), where coverage with forage peanut showed a reduction compared to treatment without coverage.

Figure 5 Plant mass and number of ground tomato fruits as a function of soil cover. Different letters differ statistically from each other, by Tukey's test at 5% probability.

The color of tomato fruits directly interferes in consumer appreciation, making it a decisive aspect for the purchase of products and their by-products. In the tomato color parameters, no significant effect was observed for luminosity and parameter a*; noticing a significant difference only for the b* parameter, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Color parameters in ground tomato as a function of ground cover. Different letters differ statistically from each other, by Tukey's test at 5% probability.

For parameter b*, which is the hue that varies from yellow to blue; in the straw cover, fruits with a hue closer to yellow were produced; while in white plastic cover and whitout mulch/hoeing the fruits had a less yellowish color. Close values were observed by Rosa et al. (2011) evaluating the color characterization

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of four Italian tomato accessions under organic management. These results corroborate this behavior of the parameter b^* in the fruits, the straw covering plants had the lowest plant-1 leaf numbers, while the highest planta-1 leaf numbers were precisely in the white plastic cover and whitout mulch/hoeing coverings. ; which had a less yellowish coloration. Fruits that are scalded by the sun, show discoloration in points of the pericarp where they are not protected by the leaves, and receive direct sunlight. The intensity of the red color of the pericarp, among other factors, is a function of the quantity and permanence of the leaves until maturity, and the consequent exposure to sunlight (CANTUÁRIO et al., 2014).

CONCLUSION

The white plastic cover showed plants with a stem diameter greater than the other covers; greater number of fruits plant-1; and fruits with less yellow pericarp coloration.

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